

Construction Cost Overrun Analysis: A Case Study of the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam Project in Kabul, Afghanistan

HASEEBULLAH HEMAT^{1*}, AHMAD SHOAIB KOHESTANI²

¹Master's Graduate of Science, Dept. of Building Construction Management, Kabul Polytechnic University, Kabul, Afghanistan. E-mail: Haseebullah.hemat2015@gmail.com

²Assistant Professor, Dept of Building Construction Management, Kabul Polytechnic University, KPU Campus, 5th District, Kabul, Afghanistan. E-mail: s.kohestani@kpu.edu.af

*Corresponding author: E-mail address: Haseebullah.hemat2015@gmail.com

Abstract — Cost overruns are a common dilemma in construction projects worldwide, resulting in financial setbacks and delays. The Shaw-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam experienced a significant cost escalation, raising concerns about the factors contributing to this increase. A comprehensive study was conducted to clarify the causes and upgrade cost estimation, Project management and risk alleviation efforts. The research findings would help stakeholders become familiar with the challenges that cause cost escalations and provide suggestions for improvement. This study reveals the previously unknown causes of cost overruns in large dam projects in Afghanistan and provides suitable solutions for decision-makers. Dam construction is one of the most expensive projects, requiring a large budget and significant commitment. To ensure the successful completion of the project within the budget, it is necessary for workers and other project stakeholders to understand the reasons for the cost escalations. This enables proper planning and reduced overhead costs, ultimately leading to successful project implementation within the budget. The author's aim was to clarify the main causes of cost overruns. Forty-six (46) factors, which were divided into six categories: project management, contracts, clients, contractors, consultants, and external factors, were found through interviews with experts, construction dam-related documents, and literature review. These factors were recognized through a quantitative survey distributed to key stakeholders in Afghan construction projects. Due to the respondents' lack of awareness of the selected topic and its related terminology, only 45 questionnaires out of 75 distributed were collected and analyzed. This caused the author to face challenges such as taking the time to describe and introduce the research topic, and limitations such as the respondents' unwillingness to provide timely responses. The questionnaires were ranked based on their relative importance index and mean value. The results highlighted 12 significant factors contributing to cost overruns in the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam Project. The four most critical factors identified were: (1) poor feasibility study, lack of enough information for the detailed design stage, irrigation and hydrological data, and poor geotechnical investigation; (2) lack of qualified and experienced technical staff (engineers); (3) poor management and contractor's experience; and (4) payment delays for work progress. Factors contributing to cost escalations in the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam Project were categorized and ranked. Consultant and design-related factors were found to have the greatest impact. Recommendations were also offered by the authors to minimize and mitigate the causes of the construction cost overruns in Afghan construction Projects.

Index Terms — Afghanistan, Construction Projects, Cost Overrun, Key Factors Causing Cost Overruns, Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam Project.

I. INTRODUCTION

COST overruns occur frequently within the construction sector around the world with more than half of all construction projects costs escalating their estimated budgeted amounts. Research shows that among all construction projects being undertaken today, about 9 out of 10 construction projects experience cost overruns between 50% and 100% [1].

The construction sector is vital for the development and growth of a country such as Afghanistan. However, cost overruns can be detrimental to the success of such projects. This research seeks to determine the factors responsible for cost overruns in the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam construction Project.

Understanding the factors for cost overruns within the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam construction Project is significant for a number of considerations, among them the important cost overruns and time delay that is estimated to be about 10 years with a cost overrun amounting to \$12.9 million. Some of the considerations for this analysis can be outlined below:

A. Economic Growth Potential

- Revenue Generation: If the project was completed on time, it would have helped generate revenue for the government from the production of electricity as well as other services such as irrigation. It would then be used for investment back into services for the benefits of economic development.
- Job Generation: Finishing the project on time would mean that jobs would be created as a result of the construction process and after the project is complete.

INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT

- Long Terms – Overall Benefits: Infrastructure development projects like the Shah-Wa-Arus multipurpose Dam construction project play a vital role in overall economic development. Overall benefits can be understood by scrutinizing the cost overruns and learning from them for improvements.

- Investment Attraction: Successful projects involving infrastructures can attract foreign investments. Looking at this case can shed significant light on improvements that can be made to attract investments.

B. Social Implications

- Community Impacts: Community unrest and disturbances can arise from project delays and cost overruns if communities are relocated and benefits expected from the project do not materialize. Understanding such aspects is critical for project planning for the future.
- Public Trust and Governance: Unnecessary delays may lead to a loss of public trust within governance structures. A detailed analysis may thus enhance public trust and accountability within governance.

LEARNING FROM MISTAKES

- Identification of Risk Factors: Analyzing the factors that might be responsible for cost overruns can identify specific risk factors such as inefficient project management, lack of stakeholder engagement, and funding constraints that might be responsible for time and cost overruns.
- Improving Project Management: The best practices and findings from this case can be used for improving project management practices and securing on-time and within-budget completion of the impending infrastructure projects.

C. Policy Implications

- Regulatory Framework: To design a proper regulatory framework for efficient project implementation, one needs to be aware of the different factors that lead to project costs overruns.
- Strategic Planning: In-depth analysis can help optimize national strategic plans for the development of infrastructure for alignment with strategic economic goals.

In conclusion, the assessment of cost overruns within the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam construction Project is critical for understanding more than the particular circumstances under which this project was beset by difficulties and for developing more general takeaways with respect to enhancing similar projects for the construction of infrastructures within Afghanistan. As such, the various consequences that can be manifested within this specific project with regard to cost overruns and other considerations tend to be far-reaching.

Concerns among the client community have increased due to the difficulties being experienced by the construction sector in implementing the projects within the schedule and cost constraints [2]. Though cost overruns occur around the world, this problem is more challenging for developing countries[3].

The construction sector is a critical one when it comes to the advancement and growth of various economies and societies worldwide; however, the ability to complete construction tasks on time and within budget is a challenge that several construction projects face, including those undertaken in Afghanistan. Findings from research conducted by [4]

demonstrate that cost overruns occur in at least 90% of construction projects undertaken the entire world and that developing countries such as Afghanistan can experience cost overruns amounting to a staggering 183% increase from the estimated project cost. These findings are important and gives this research the critical chance to establish a powerful discussion on the effects of cost overruns on the growth and development of both the economy and society of Afghanistan within the context of the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam construction Project.

The construction sector is very important for the development of Afghanistan and contributes around 10% to the GDP. However, some factors such as lack of productivity and client dissatisfaction hinder the growth of the economy and foreign direct investments within the construction sector[5].

This thesis highlights the cost overruns drivers in the construction sector within Afghanistan and particularly within the project: The Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam construction. It aims at improving project planning and risk management approaches and thereby contributing towards increased understanding and project success within Afghanistan.

II. OVERVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

The issue of cost overruns is a global phenomenon, especially in the construction industry. In most cases, cost overrun has consequently led to disputes among the client, consultants, and contractors on the variation in project costs. Clients are usually at risk when construction projects are faced with cost overruns. According to a study conducted by [6], cost overruns in construction industries worldwide have become a continued problem whose causes remain debated. Fluctuations in material prices remain the most potent factor that contributes to cost overruns in developing countries. Some of the common problems associated with cost overruns in developing countries include poor management of the project, incorrect estimation, and contractor financial status.

A research study in Brazil focused on cost overruns and delays in megaprojects. Results indicate that megaprojects carry with them inherent risks and challenges; for instance, construction costs increased by an average of 97.5%, while the duration of projects increased by 74.28% over original estimates [7].

In a study by[8], the reasons for delay and cost overruns in construction projects were analyzed in Afghanistan. The top factors causing time overruns included security challenges, corruption, and difficulties with project financing. The main cause of cost overruns included improper site management, construction accidents, and inappropriate selection of technical staff. In this study, 106 questionnaires were forwarded to construction professionals; 101 responses were received, which included 34 from managers, 24 from engineers and consultants, 10 from owners and clients, and 23 from contractors. Ten responses were incomplete and did not have much value for analysis. In this respect, 91 responses were identified as valid for further investigation.

In a study conducted by [9], the key causes of cost and schedule overruns were identified for small dam construction projects. Key causes identified include delays in land

acquisition, deficient project planning and management, design errors, lack of qualified staff, poor site management, inefficient use of technology, and shortage of qualified staff for design. These issues commonly contribute to the overruns within small dam projects in Pakistan. The study identified the implementation of proper project management tools and methodologies to handle these challenges.

Regarding time and cost overruns in large projects, a study conducted by [10] identified the root causes as a lack of project-specific experience, past decisions made by external entities and by the organization itself, community resistance, and stakeholder-driven scope changes. In mitigating overruns, the study advocates for a strategy addressing the project, organizational, and external environments. Linking the factors identified from both studies shows how particular elements, such as stakeholder engagement and project management methods, may influence one another differently under different circumstances. For example, the lack of project-specific experience identified by [10] could exacerbate other shortcomings such as poor site management highlighted by Anwar, as these issues are somewhat interlinked. By allowing the integration of relevant issues into one article, the review has become a more holistic piece, providing a broader insight into the causes of cost overruns in construction projects.

In the critical analysis conducted by [11], a study in the UAE construction industry investigated the causes of time and cost overruns. The five main causes of time overrun were design variations, unrealistic schedules, permit delays, inaccurate time estimation, and change orders. Correspondingly, the five leading causes of cost overruns were design variations, poor cost estimation, decision-making delays, financial constraints, and inappropriate procurement methods.

Poor productivity, lack of early planning, delayed completion, and shortage in skilled resources and motivation were the major causes for cost overruns identified in a UAE construction industry study by [12].

For instance, [13] studied factors influencing cost overruns in micro-scaled construction companies. From the results, design changes, constructability problems, and delays in design approvals were determined as the critical factors that would lead to cost overruns in such firms.

Bureaucracy seems to present a serious challenge to the infrastructure sector in Afghanistan, as it does in many other countries. This trait prevents work from being done in infrastructure projects and, therefore, acts as a hindrance toward reaching the country's strategic economic goals.

The literature review explains the problem of cost overruns, which is common in construction projects across the globe, and thus poses a significant financial risk to clients. Some of the most frequently found causes include poor management, incorrect material estimates, and prices, especially in developing countries. Many studies that emanated from Afghanistan, Malaysia, Brazil, Saudi Arabia, India, and Nigeria found that the factors that contribute to cost overruns include low productivity, lack of proper planning, delays in completing the projects, and changes in design.

Certain challenges are identified from these studies, including security issues, corruption, financing problems, and poor site management. The review emphasizes how effective project

management, enhanced procurement practices, and more effective coordination among the relevant players will help minimize cost overruns. In essence, the findings suggest that cost overruns are a complex issue with technical, economic, psychological, and political factors, which need a holistic approach for any effective solutions.

By studying a wide array of literature and with expert interviews, an in-depth analysis is able to identify forty-six different causes relating to project cost overruns. These causes were categorized into six categories, as demonstrated in Table 1.

TABLE I
COST OVERRUN CAUSES THAT ARE FREQUENTLY DISCOVERED.

No.	Factors that Lead to Cost Overruns	The categorization
Project Management-Related Factors		
1.	Poor construction and project management	
2.	Payment delays for work progress	
3.	The lack of a risk management strategy	
4.	Schedules that are too optimistic or are without consideration for risks	
5.	Inadequate commissioning/start-up strategy	
Contract Related Factors		
1.	Incompetent bidding and awarding procedure	
2.	Selecting of inappropriate kind of contract	
3.	Inappropriate terms and conditions in contracts	
4.	Not adhering to the contract terms by neglecting to certify the required approvals	
5.	Delay in signing of changed contract amendments	
Client Related Factors		
1.	Changes in orders and scope, and additional work during construction	
2.	Delay in reviewing and approving design and other technical documents	
3.	Inadequate qualified and experienced technical staff (engineers)	
4.	Client's suspension of work	
5.	The decision-making process is lengthy	
6.	Changes in the design	
7.	Contractual claims	
8.	Poor construction inspection	
9.	Delayed site transfer to the contractor	
10.	Poor control of costs	
Contractor Related Factors		
1.	Delivery of specialized equipment from outside of the country and to the construction site	
2.	Delay in the project's construction phases	
3.	Occurring technical problems during the construction stage	
4.	Increasing the amount of excavation and quantity of materials in the foundation during construction	
5.	Poor management and experience of the contractor	
6.	Contractor's financial difficulties.	
7.	Unsuccessful planning, and scheduling, and providing of project recovery schedule	
8.	Delayed payment from contractor to sub-contractor and suppliers	
9.	Delay in review of design, drawings, and contract documents	
10.	Contractor's claims	
11.	Error caused by inadequate method during the construction phase	
Consultant and Design-Related Factors		
1.	Poor feasibility study, lack of enough information for the detailed design Stage, Irrigation, hydrological data, and poor geotechnical Investigation	
2.	Mistake in providing the project design and drawing package, and other technical documents for the client approval	
3.	Inadequate inspection strategy by consultants	
4.	Poor management and experience of the consultant	
External Related Factors		
1.	Delay due to governmental bureaucracy	
2.	Cultural and social factors	
3.	Convolutions in politics	
4.	Climatic conditions.	
5.	Permits approval from authorities	
6.	Market inflation and currency fluctuations	
7.	Land acquisition.	
8.	A Natural Disaster (Flood)	
9.	Force majeure (delay due to the Covid-19 pandemic)	

III .RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To identify and prioritize the causes of cost escalation in the Shah-Wa-Arus project, primary and secondary data were used. The primary data were obtained through the distribution of questionnaires and interviews with employees of the Ministry of Energy and Water and project stakeholders, and the secondary data was obtained through the study of previous studies and literature reviews. The questionnaire employed both open-ended and Likert-scale questions to assess the agreement among respondents. The people who were directly involved in the project, including department heads, project managers, engineers, contractors, and other team members, were the focus of this research.

The Research data were collected through the questionnaire and a pilot survey, which were evaluated and finalized through Google Forms and SPSS software. Almost 40 percent of the evaluation was conducted by Google Form. The evaluation

process included ranking values by choosing ranks classified as low, medium, and high. To ensure the accuracy of the data analysis and secure reliable results, for the rest of 60 percent of the assessment, SPSS (statistical package for the social sciences) software and MS Office Excel were used.

The study's relevance and impact might be significantly increased by elucidating how the results relate to and enhance the existing body of knowledge. The importance of the study might be significantly increased by explaining how the findings relate to and upgrade the present body of knowledge. Such a context would not only situate the findings in the broader discussion on cost overruns but highlight their implications for future research and practice. This gap may provide a greater impact for the study and also provides a better understanding of the difficulties.

To think rationally, using the Relative Importance Index (RII) is very worthwhile in this setting.

Quantitative analysis: RII enables the methodical and numerical assessment of the importance of several factors contributing to cost escalation. This enables a better understanding of the relative effects of the various components, which is crucial in construction projects where multiple factors interact.

Stakeholders Viewpoints: RII put together a range of viewpoints that represent the realities of the Project management in the Afghan construction sectors by integrating input from main stakeholders.

Factor ranking: RII assesses challenges that need to be addressed right away by clearly ranking factors according to their importance. This is essential for decision-makers who want to successfully address the most significant roots of cost escalations.

Comparative Analysis: By allowing comparisons between distinct factors, the RII method makes it simpler to mark patterns and connections that are not visible when using only qualitative methods.

Adaptability: RII is a useful tool for investigating cost escalation in this study. It is also adaptable in a variety of situations, including construction Projects, so it can also be used in subsequent research

By using RII, the study enhances its methodological rigor and ensures that the results are reliable, which contributes to the project management practices within the construction industry. Cost escalation is ranked in this study based on the Relative Importance Index. The formulas from [14] and [15] are used to determine the RII value, equation (1)

$$RII = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 W_i * X_i}{A * X} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where:

- RII: Relative important index
- W: Respondent's weight on scale of 1 to 5, related to each factor according to its important.
- X: Frequency reaction of each cause.
- A: cause with the large weight (5, in this example)
- N: The number of people who answered

Quantitative research methodologies were used in this study to assess afghan construction Professional's point of view of the reasons of the cost escalation. And questionnaires were distributed to determine the essential causes of cost escalation

in construction projects across the nation. In order to estimate the data and specify the level of significance.

In order to find the reasons of the cost escalation, a pilot interview was made with the 11 professionals who had the project management roles in the Project of Shah-Wa-Arus Dam. The factors were found in these interviews then spreader out for a survey and delved into. The 74 revised questionnaire distributed to professionals included clients' consultants and contractors.

Quantitative research methodologies were used in this study to assess afghan construction Professional's point of view of the reasons of the cost escalation. And questionnaires were distributed to determine the essential causes of cost escalation in construction projects across the nation. In order to estimate the data and specify the level of significance.

In order to find the reasons of the cost escalation, a pilot interview was made with the 11 professionals who had the project management roles in the Project of Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam construction. The factors were found in these interviews then spreader out for a survey and delved into. The 74 revised questionnaire distributed to professionals included clients' consultants and contractors.

IV. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

To certify accurate responses and improve the validity of the research, attempts were addressed toward engaging individuals with substantial knowledge of the project or experience in executing similar projects.

The questionnaire survey was distributed online via Google Forms where all respondents were allowed to have access and complete it through various devices without requiring of Physical copies. A simplified submission process link was provided through their emails and smartphone, while the data saved and analysis automatically by software.

Consequently, interviews with the persons concerned in the construction industry, including senior engineers, contractors, and company owners, were conducted to gather insights for the literature Review. The same questions from the questionnaire were asked. In these interviews, the interpretations and opinions gathered from the findings were integrated into the study's analysis and recommendations.

However, this research encountered several challenges and limitations during its preparation. There was a delay in responding, as some respondents found the chosen topic and its associated terminology difficult to understand. This lack of understanding caused additional time for explanations and clarifications. Furthermore, respondents did not show motivation to provide timely feedback.

A structured questionnaire survey was conducted by distributing a total of 74 sets of questionnaires. Out of the 74 questionnaires distributed to employees of the Ministry of Energy and Water (MEW) in Afghanistan and contractor staff working on the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam project, 45 questionnaires were returned and considered usable for further analysis, as indicated in Table 2.

TABLE II
SUMMARY OF THE CONDUCTED SURVEY

Characteristics	Values
The total number of distributed questionnaires	74
The total number of received questionnaires	45
Percentage of completed received responses (%)	60.8
Percentage of valid responses for analysis received (%)	60.8

A. Characteristics of the Survey Conducted

Amongst the survey participants, the largest group was represented by clients, accounting for 62.2% of respondents, followed by contractors at 22.2% and consultants at the third level at 15.6%. Regarding their educational background, the majority of participants held a Master's degree, representing 53.3% of the respondents. Additionally, 42.2% of participants held a bachelor's degree, while 2 respondents had a diploma qualification.

The job positions of the respondents suggest that the majority of participants were engineers, constituting 64.4% of the respondents. Additionally, 17.8% of participants held the role of project managers, while 15.6% were identified as heads of departments.

Among the respondents, 13 individuals had over 10 years of experience in the construction industry. 14 respondents had 5-10 years of experience, 10 respondents had between 3-5 years of experience, while 8 respondents were relatively new, having between 1-3 years of experience.

The construction of Shah-Wa-Arus is only funded by the Afghan government, while the Ministry of Water and Energy takes care of all construction and technical processes. This ministry is in charge of planning, managing, surveying, designing, and implementing water and energy infrastructures, which requires a huge number of technical staff, much more than any private contracting company or consultancy in Afghanistan can ever provide.

As a result, most respondents in this research are related to the client, who is actively involved in the technical processes and implementation of projects under the Ministry of Water and Energy (MEW), especially the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam construction project. Most of these professionals have more than ten years of experience and hold master's degrees. To increase credibility and ensure accurate and reliable results, the study focused on experienced and highly educated personnel, including engineers, project managers, and heads of department.

The second and third levels of respondents include contractors and consultants involved in the project who have adequate experience, as outlined in the table below. It is worth noting that many respondents are engineers who are involved in similar projects, including the Shah-Wa-Arus Dam, providing them with relevant knowledge and expertise. The second level also includes a large number of project managers. Given that there were many managers involved in this project during its life span (15 years), eight of them were identified, and relevant data were collected to achieve accurate results and increase the validity of the study; their views and opinions were also included in this research and survey.

Its worth to mention in order to obtain an accurate answer to the research results and increase the credibility of the research,

an effort was made to focus more on those who had sufficient knowledge of the project or had experience in implementing similar projects.

B. Ranking of cost overruns factors

This study phase involved analyzing cost-overrun factors based on questionnaire responses. Each of the six sections that make up the research section's 46 chosen factors is examined and ranked separately.

1) Cost Overrun Project Management Related Factors

According to the study, cost overruns are significantly impacted by project management factors, which have been ranked according to their significance. "Poor coordination and communication between project parties" came in second with a mean score of 3.53, while "poor construction and project management" came in top with a mean score of 3.76. These findings are explained by the lack of project managers and construction managers in Afghanistan as a result of years of conflict and a lack of construction expertise. These issues need to be addressed to ensure quality, budget control, timely completion, safety, stakeholders' satisfaction, reputation, future opportunities, and better compliance with regulations. In contrast, "lack of risk management strategy" ranks lowest in this group, with a mean value of 3.20.

TABLE III
RESPONDENTS DEMOGRAPHICS

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative (%)
Type of Institution			
Client	28	62.2	62.2
Contractor	10	22.2	84.4
Consultant	7	15.6	100
Respondent Education Level			
Master	24	53.3	53.3
Bachelor	19	42.2	95.5
Diploma	2	4.5	100
Respondents Designation			
Engineer	29	64.4	64.4
Project Manager	8	17.8	82.2
Head of Department	7	15.6	97.8
Other	1	2.2	100
Relevant Working Experience on Construction Projects			
5-10 years	14	31.1	31.1
>10 years	13	28.9	60
3-5 years	10	22.2	82.2
1-3 years	8	17.8	100

TABLE IV
COST OVERRUN PROJECT MANAGEMENT RELATED FACTORS

Descriptive Statistics					
No.	Factors	N	Mean	RII	Rank
1	Poor construction and project management	45	3.76	0.75	1
2	Poor coordination and communication between the project's parties	45	3.53	0.7	2
3	Schedules that are too optimistic or are without consideration for risks	45	3.27	0.65	3

4	Inadequate commissioning/start-up strategy	45	3.22	0.64	4
5	The lack of a risk management strategy	45	3.20	0.64	5
	Valid N (listwise)	45			

*N-indicates the respondent's number

Fig.1. Cost Overrun Project Management Related Factors

2) Cost Overruns Contract Related Factors

Factors related to contracts have a significant impact on cost overruns and are ranked in order of importance. "Delay in signing contract amendments" ranks first with mean value of 3.44, followed by "Choosing inappropriate contract types" with a mean value of 3.42. Timely execution of contract amendments is vital to reducing cost overruns. Challenges in Afghanistan includes allocating work to suitable individuals and selecting the right project delivery type, often due to the lower qualifications of contractors. The factor with the lowest ranking in this group is "incompetent bidding and awarding procedure," with a mean value of 3.27.

TABLE V
COST OVERRUNS CONTRACT RELATED FACTORS

Descriptive Statistics					
No.	Factors	N	Mean	RII	Rank
1	Delay in signing of changed contract amendments.	45	3.44	0.68	1
2	Selecting of inappropriate kind of contract.	45	3.42	0.68	2
3	Not adhering to the contract terms by neglecting to certify the required approvals.	45	3.31	0.66	3
4	Inappropriate terms and conditions in contracts.	45	3.31	0.66	4
5	Incompetent bidding and awarding procedure.	45	3.27	0.65	5
	Valid N (listwise)	45			

*N-indicates the respondent's number

3) Cost Overrun Client Related Factors

Factors related to client involvement have a significant impact on cost overruns and were ranked by importance. "Inadequate qualified and experienced technical staff (engineers)" ranked first with a mean value of 4.00, followed by "payment delays for work progress" with a mean value of 3.93. Addressing the issue of qualified and experienced technical staff, particularly engineers, is crucial to mitigating cost overruns and ensuring accurate estimation, efficient resource allocation, effective risk management, and timely resolution of technical problems. The

delay in progress payments ranked second and can lead to liquidity depletion for contractors, causing delays and cost overruns. Other factors include scope changes, unrealistic contract durations, and delayed site transfer to the contractor, which received the lowest ranking.

Fig. 2. Cost Overruns Contract Related Factors

TABLE VI
COST OVERRUN CLIENT RELATED FACTORS

Descriptive Statistics					
No.	Factors	N	Mean	RII	Rank
1	Inadequate qualified and experienced technical staff (engineers).	45	4.00	0.8	1
2	Payment delays for work progress.	45	3.93	0.786	2
3	Changes in orders and scope, and additional work during construction.	45	3.87	0.77	3
4	Poor construction inspection.	45	3.87	0.77	4
5	Changes in the design.	45	3.84	0.76	5
6	Delay in reviewing and approving design and other technical documents.	45	3.76	0.75	6
7	Client's suspension of work.	45	3.69	0.73	7
8	Contractual claims.	45	3.56	0.71	8
9	The decision-making process is lengthy.	45	3.56	0.71	9
10	Poor control of costs.	45	3.51	0.7	10
11	Delayed site transfer to the contractor.	45	3.20	0.64	11
	Valid N (listwise)	45			

*N-indicates the respondent's number

Fig.3. Cost Overrun Client Related Factors

4) Cost Overrun Contractor Related Factors

Factors related to contractors have a significant impact on project cost overruns and were ranked by importance. "Poor management and experience of the contractor" obtained the highest ranking with a mean value of 3.98, followed by "Contractor's financial difficulties" with a mean value of 3.87. However, addressing management and lack of experience is highly important for managing cost overruns for such aspects as cost estimation and allocation, management of subcontractors and change orders, management of schedules and quality, and overall risk management. The factor with the lowest mean ranking is "delayed payment from contractor to sub-contractor and suppliers," at 3.29

TABLE VII
COST OVERRUN CONTRACTOR RELATED FACTORS

Descriptive Statistics					
No.	Factors	N	Mean	RII	Rank
1	Poor management and experience of the contractor.	45	3.98	0.79	1
2	Contractor's financial difficulties.	45	3.87	0.77	2
3	Occurring technical problems during the construction stage.	45	3.62	0.72	3
4	Unsuccessful planning, scheduling, and providing of project recovery schedule.	45	3.53	0.7	4
5	Increasing the amount of excavation and quantity of materials in the foundation During Construction.	45	3.47	0.69	5
6	Delay in the project's construction phases.	45	3.44	0.68	6
7	Error caused by inadequate method during the construction phase	45	3.42	0.68	7
8	Contractor's claims.	45	3.40	0.68	8
9	Delivery of specialized equipment from outside of the Country and to the Construction site.	45	3.38	0.67	9
10	Delay in review of design, drawings, and contract documents	45	3.33	0.66	10
11	Delayed payment from contractor to sub-contractor and suppliers.	45	3.29	0.65	11
	Valid N (listwise)	45			

*N-indicates the respondent's number

Fig.4. Cost Overrun Contractor Related Factors

5) Cost Overrun Consultant and Design Related Factors

The factors involving consultants and design influence cost overruns substantially and were ordered based on their relative importance. "Poor feasibility study, lack of sufficient information for the detailed design stage, irrigation and hydrological data, and poor geotechnical investigation" was given the highest ranking with a mean value of 4.00. "Poor management and experience of the consultant" was given the second-highest ranking with a mean value of 3.67. It is important to consider factors such as inadequate feasibility studies, lack of sufficient information for detailed design stages, and management and experience of the consultant for proper cost management and for preventing cost overruns for the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam construction project. A proper feasibility study, sufficient information for the detailed design stage, and qualified consultants can help deal with difficulties and can be beneficial for proper estimation and utilization of resources for efficient construction and management. The factor with the lowest ranking is "mistake in design package and technical documents," with a mean value of 3.38.

TABLE VIII
COST OVERRUNS FACTORS RELATED CONSULTANT AND DESIGN

Descriptive Statistics					
No.	Factors	N	Mean	RII	Rank
1	Poor feasibility study, lack of enough information for the detailed design Stage, Irrigation, and hydrological data and poor geotechnical Investigation.	45	4.00	0.8	1
2	Poor management and experience of the consultant.	45	3.67	0.73	2
3	Delay in providing the project design and drawing package, and other technical documents for the client approval.	45	3.67	0.73	3
4	Inadequate inspection strategy by consultants.	45	3.53	0.7	4
5	Mistake in design package and technical documents.	45	3.38	0.67	5
	Valid N (listwise)	45			

*N-indicates the respondent's number

Fig.5. Cost Overrun Consultant and Design Related Factors

6) External Related Cost Overruns Factors

Factors related to external cost escalations had a significant impact and were ranked base on their importance. "Land acquisition" ranked first with a mean value of 3.78 and "delay due to government bureaucracy" ranked second with a mean value of 3.31. Addressing the challenges related to land acquisition and reducing the impact of government bureaucracy to minimize cost escalations in the Shah-Va-Arus Multipurpose Dam project is a very important issue. Efficient land acquisition processes, active community involvement, prior consideration of environmental factors, simplified administrative procedures, improved decision-making, coordination between agencies, and timely release of funding can help mitigate these cost overruns factors. The factor with the lowest ranking is "natural disaster (flood)," with a mean value of 2.91.

TABLE IX
COST OVERRUN EXTERNAL RELATED FACTORS

Descriptive Statistics					
No.	Factors	N	Mean	RII	Rank
1	Land acquisition	45	3.78	0.755	1
2	Delay due to governmental bureaucracy	45	3.31	0.66	2
3	Force Majeure (Delay due to the Covid-19 pandemic)	45	3.29	0.65	3
4	Convolutions in politics	45	3.22	0.64	4
5	Permits approval from authorities	45	3.16	0.63	5
6	Market inflation and currency fluctuations	45	3.11	0.62	6
7	Cultural and social factors	45	3.04	0.6	7
8	Climatic conditions	45	2.93	0.58	8
9	A Natural Disaster (Flood)	45	2.91	0.58	9
	Valid N (listwise)	45			

*N-indicates the respondent's number

Fig. 6. Cost Overrun External Related Factors

C. Ranking Categories That Have A Negative Impact On Project Cost

The analysis identified six categories as causes of cost overruns in projects. These categories have been classified and ranked, as shown in Table 10, highlighting their negative impact on project costs.

TABLE X
RANKING CATEGORIES THAT HAVE A NEGATIVE IMPACT ON PROJECT COST

Descriptive Statistics					
	Factors	N	Mean	RII	Rank
1	Consultant and Design-Related Factors	45	4.00	0.8	1
2	Client Related Factors	45	4.00	0.8	2
3	Contractor Related Factors	45	3.98	0.79	3
4	External Related Factors	45	3.78	0.75	4
5	Project Management Related Factors	45	3.76	0.75	5
6	Contract Related Factors	45	3.44	0.68	6
	Valid N (listwise)	45			

*N-indicates the respondent's number

Fig.7. Ranking Categories that have a negative impact on project cost

1) The Top 12 Factors Caused Costs Overrun

The top 12 causes of cost overruns are ranked based on their mean values and relative importance index, as shown in Table 11. As per the survey, the most prevalent causes of cost overruns are related to factors such as a "poor feasibility study, lack of enough information for the detailed design stage, irrigation, and hydrological data, and poor geotechnical investigation," ranking first. The second cause is attributed to "inadequate qualified and experienced technical staff (engineers)," followed by "poor management and experience of the contractor" in third place. The fourth cause is "payment delays for work progress," while the fifth cause is "the contractor's financial difficulties." The sixth cause is associated with "changes in orders and scope, and additional work during construction," and the seventh cause is "poor construction inspection." "Changes in the design" ranks eighth, followed by "land acquisition" in ninth place. The tenth cause is "delay in reviewing and approving design and other technical documents," while "poor construction and project management" ranks eleventh, and "client's suspension

of work" is twelfth. The causes, their respective mean values, and the relative importance index have been calculated, analyzed, and provided below.

TABLE XI
TOP 12 FACTORS CAUSING COST OVERRUN IN THE SHAH-WA-ARUS MULTIPURPOSE DAM CONSTRUCTION PROJECT

Descriptive Statistics					
No.	Factors	N	Mean	RII	Rank
1	Poor feasibility study, lack of enough information for the detailed design Stage, Irrigation, and hydrological data and poor geotechnical Investigation.	45	4	0.8	1
2	Inadequate qualified and experienced technical staff (Engineers).	45	4	0.8	2
3	Poor management and experience of the contractor.	45	3.98	0.79	3
4	Payment delays for work progress.	45	3.93	0.78	4
5	Contractor's financial difficulties.	45	3.87	0.77	5
6	Changes in orders and scope, and additional work during construction.	45	3.87	0.77	6
7	Poor construction inspection.	45	3.87	0.77	7
8	Changes in the design.	45	3.84	0.76	8
9	Land acquisition.	45	3.78	0.75	9
10	Delay in reviewing and approving design and other technical documents.	45	3.76	0.75	10
11	Poor construction and project management	45	3.76	0.75	11
12	Client's suspension of work.	45	3.69	0.73	12
	Valid N (listwise)	45			

*N-indicates the respondent's number

Fig.8. Top 12 factors causing cost overrun in the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam Construction Project

V. CONCLUSION

This, in brief, was an attempt to uncover the drivers of cost overruns in the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam Project in Kabul, Afghanistan. Cost overruns are one of the important obstacles to Afghanistan's construction scene. Following a review of the literature and consultation with experts, we identified 46 cost overruns causes. Data collection was done in Afghanistan through a structured questionnaire by distributing 74 questionnaires to the selected clients, consultants, and contractors, out of which 45 valid data were returned that were analyzed. The first 12 causes ranked based on the mean values and RII are presented in the table below; Table 11: First 12 Overruns Causes. The survey indicates that the most dominant cost overruns arise from factors such as poor feasibility study, lack of enough information for the detailed design stage, irrigation, and hydrological data, and poor geotechnical investigation, ranking first. Inadequate qualified and experienced technical staff (engineers), stands second, and poor management and experience of the contractor in third place. In fourth place, there are payment delays for work progress and, on fifth place, the contractor's financial difficulties. On the sixth place, changes in orders and scope, and additional work during construction. The seventh cause is poor construction inspection. The eighth is the design changes, the ninth is land acquisition, the tenth is delay in reviewing and approving the design and other technical documents, the eleventh, poor construction and project management, and the twelfth place is taken by client's suspension of work. The table also gives the calculated means and relative importance index (RII) of these causes.

Political instability, security problems, and infrastructures difficulties are not trivial in Afghanistan construction projects. However, political factors are considered external factors in this study and rank fourth with an RII of 0.64 in this category, though they do not feature within the first twelve most significant overall causes, indicating that their impact on cost overruns for the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam construction project is limited. Other reasons are not included for several reasons:

- Technical aspects: The focus is biased towards technical and managerial issues rather than broader context; hence, Afghanistan-specific difficulties might be missed.
- Data availability: Limited access to reliable political and security information can constrain analysis.

Scope of the research: Narrow focus may inadvertently exclude broader contextual factors considered less relevant to the analysis at hand.

Preparation was plagued by a number of challenges and limitations. A number of the respondents did not fully understand the topic and the terminology used, necessitating further explanation with consequent inefficiencies. Motivation to respond in good time was also not consistent. Follow-ups were needed to enhance response rates and quality apart from repeated contact and several emails that were time-consuming. Out of 74 questionnaires, 45 were useful for analysis. A few respondents were still not willing to respond even after being assured of confidentiality. Despite these challenges, the study achieved its objectives.

Key findings reveal that the major cost overruns factors for the Shah-Wa-Arus Multipurpose Dam project are: (1) a poor feasibility study, lack of enough information for the detailed design stage, irrigation, and hydrological data, and poor geotechnical investigation; (2) poor management and experience of the contractor; (3) poor management and experience of the contractor; and (4) payment delays for work progress.

The study highlighted that consultant and design-related factors had the greatest influence. This will provide valuable insight to stakeholders in seeking better plans, management, and communications as ways of avoiding cost increases and achieving successful outcomes. It also calls for the need to strengthen construction sector capability in Afghanistan to reduce overruns and project failures.

The selection of an experienced and qualified consultant for studies, design, and tender documentation and qualified contractors will ensure successful execution without overruns and delays. Similarly, good construction supervision is required. Compatibility between budget and schedule reduces the financial complications brought by good planning and allocation of resources. Also, timely decisions related to labor contract claims, with the help of arbitration, resolve disputes and avoid delays and extra costs. Since there is a shortage of engineers, it is also critical that investment in training and development programs for the project team will pay off in terms of having qualified personnel responsible for managing and executing the project. Further research should be directed toward strategies for mitigating cost overruns in the Afghan construction industry and examining the interrelationships among their causes more completely.

REFERENCES

- [1] O. J. Ameh, A. A. Soyingbe, and K. T. Odusami, "Significant factors causing cost overruns in telecommunication projects in Nigeria," *J. Constr. Dev. Ctries.*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 49–67, 2010.
- [2] Ahmad S et al., "Construction Delays in Florida: An Empirical Study. Final Report. Department of Community Affairs, Florida, US," no. August, 2002.
- [3] Nida Azhar et.al, "Cost Overrun Factors In Construction Industry of Pakistan," Karachi,, Pakistan: First International Conference on Construction In Developing Countries (ICCIDC-I) "Advancing and Integrating Construction Education, Research & Practice," 2008.
- [4] B. Flyvbjerg, M. K. Skamris Holm, and S. L. Buhl, "What causes cost overrun in transport infrastructure projects?," *Transp. Rev.*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 3–18, 2004, doi: 10.1080/0144164032000080494a.
- [5] Afghanistan Investment Support Agency(AISA), "Annual Report Of Afghanistan Investment Support Agency," Kabul, 2012.
- [6] S. Ahady, S. Gupta, and R. K. Malik, "A study of the causes of cost overrun in construction industry in Afghanistan," *Int. J. Eng. Dev. Res.*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 978–985, 2017.
- [7] C. Callegari, A. Szklo, and R. Schaeffer, "Cost overruns and delays in energy megaprojects: How big is big enough?," *Energy Policy*, vol. 114, no. November 2017, pp. 211–220, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2017.11.059.
- [8] Irshad Habibi, "Investigation on Causes of Delays and Cost Overruns of Construction Projects in Afghanistan," *J. Manag. Inf. Decis. Sci.*, vol. 6, no. 4, 2023.
- [9] H. M. A. Anwar, "An Investigation into Critical Causes of Cost and Schedule Overrun in Construction of Small Dam Projects," 2021, [Online]. Available: [https://thesis.cust.edu.pk/UploadedFiles/Hafiz Muhammad Awais Anwar-MEM191002.pdf](https://thesis.cust.edu.pk/UploadedFiles/Hafiz%20Muhammad%20Awais%20Anwar-MEM191002.pdf)
- [10] S. Simushi and J. Wium, "Time and cost overruns on large projects: Understanding the root cause," *J. Constr. Dev. Ctries.*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 129–146, 2020, doi: 10.21315/jcdc2020.25.1.7.
- [11] R. M. Johnson and R. I. I. Babu, "Time and cost overruns in the UAE construction industry: a critical analysis," *Int. J. Constr. Manag.*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 402–411, 2020, doi: 10.1080/15623599.2018.1484864.
- [12] Muralidaran Ramabhadran, "An Investigation into Cost Overrun in Construction Projects in United Arab Emirates," *Int. J. Constr. Eng. Manag.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–21, 2018.
- [13] G. Polat, F. Okay, and E. Eray, "Factors affecting cost overruns in micro-scaled construction companies," *Procedia Eng.*, vol. 85, pp. 428–435, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.proeng.2014.10.569.
- [14] D. Megha and B. Rajiv, "A Methodology for Ranking of Causes of Delay for Residential Construction Projects in Indian Context," no. August, 2019.
- [15] A. Enshassi, S. Mohamed, and S. Abushaban, "Factors affecting the performance of Construction projects in the Gaza Strip," *J. Civ. Eng. Manag.*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 269–280, 2009, doi: 10.3846/1392-3730.2009.15.269-280.